

INFRASTRUCTURAL AND STAFF DEVELOPMENT IN PUBLIC TERTIARY EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS BY THE TETFUND: EVIDENCE FROM KWARA STATE, NIGERIA

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16614240>

Keywords:

*TET Fund,
Infrastructural
development,
Human
development,
Research funding,
Colleges of
education*

Abstract: *The paper examined the contribution of the TETFund to infrastructural and human developments as well as the funding of research by public tertiary education institutions in Kwara State. Since 2011, TETFund has been providing infrastructural and human development, but there is little literature available outside of what the Fund itself has published regarding its activities on both a nationwide and zonal basis. The study was created to investigate the perception of stakeholders in public universities about TETFund's quantum support for development of these key areas in Kwara State. Three questions were addressed. The mixed-methods design was adopted (both quantitative and qualitative approaches) of the study, while two states sampled in the selection of institutions and participant (multistage sampling procedure). Data was collected through checklist and interview guide. All collected data were analysed using frequency, percentage and thematic analysis. The findings show that TETFund is the only long-lasting funding organisation that significantly supports building infrastructure, developing people, and funding research in public colleges in Kwara State, regardless of whether they are owned by the national or local government. The governments had virtually hands-off infrastructural and staff development, leaving TETFund to carry out this function and fund research. It was concluded that TETFund was fulfilling its mandate and thus, should be further strengthened.*

Introduction

Tertiary education provision anywhere in the world is pivotal to self and national development.

This is so, as this subsector of the national economy is responsible for providing high-level human capital to drive national development. It

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is, therefore, essential to fund the subsector adequately for national emancipation. According to FRN (2004), higher or tertiary education is post-secondary education. Higher education institutions in Nigeria include polytechnics, monotechnics, colleges of education, and universities. The subsector, which produces the bulk of this calibre of human capital, has faced a shortage of funding for decades (Akinwole, 2020 and Ogunyemi, 2020). The problem has continued to escalate from year to year up to the present day. For instance, from 1992 to 2022, there is hardly any year without industrial dispute between higher education institutions' unions and government at both the federal and state levels, due to the poor teaching and learning conditions in Nigeria's public higher institutions (Onuka, 2017). The constant disputes between the government and ASUU led to the establishment of the Education Tax Fund in 1992, which has led to significant improvements in funding for PHEIs.

Much more work is needed because TETFund serves only as an intervention program and cannot replace a consistent source of adequate funding for PHEIs. Much still needs to be done because TETFund is only an intervention program that cannot replace a regular source of adequate funding for PHEIs. Besides, it has its definite mandates, which are rather complement. This is why the demand for adequate funding of PHEIs has not diminished and is unlikely to be established until a sustainable funding model for infrastructure in PHEIs is established. Limit of the available funds to PHEIs. This is why agitation for adequate funding of PHEIs has not abated and is not likely

to until a sustainable funding model for funding infrto in PHEIs emerges. The essence of having a prudent use of available funds is crucial for maintaining a sustainable inflow of funds within the campuses to create a conducive learning environment. Onuka et al. (2025) posited that also ensuring that available funds are prudently utilised is essential to having a sustainable inflow of funds. This statement is supported by (Ayeni and Andeshi, 2023) who asserted that mismanagement is evident as university education in Nigeria, like other public sector institutions, suffers from a considerable number of uncompleted or abandoned projects. Onuka (2017) submitted that it is one thing to adequately provide funds to NPHEIs, but it is another thing entirely to ensure that funds are appropriately utilised through prudent fund management. Thus, a fund utilisation monitoring system will ensure that embezzlement, misapplication, misappropriation, and mismanagement of the available fund to PHEIs are avoided and value for money is obtained, especially in terms of infrastructural developments in the Nigerian public institutions, with special reference to Kwara State.

As noted by Onuka (2005), it is salient to observe that the budgetary allocations to the education sector are usually inclusive of agencies and parastatals and just for educational institutions. He also found out that the available fund was being distributed among education institutions, the Ministry of Education, and education agencies. He also reported that as of 2002, there were twenty-two agencies within the education level, and the number was similarly

close and not so different in the sub-nation with a significant room for improvement. As for this study, many more were added, as had been added on board, as had the number of extra ministerial departments and educational institutions. Such development has further depleted the available amount earmarked for tertiary education institutional infrastructural developments.

Onuka (2017) pointed out that the unplanned establishment of a multiplicity of public institutions of higher learning by both the federal and state governments, which is often politically motivated, has contributed to the aggravation of the funding challenge facing PHEIs (universities, polytechnics, and colleges of education) in the country and, therefore, by extension, institutional infrastructural development in our public higher education space. Unfortunately, while infrastructural decay has continued almost unabated, except for their reliance on TETFund intervention for capital projects, both federal and state governments have. Despite the ongoing establishment of new public higher education institutions, budgetary allocations for infrastructural development have not matched this growth. It is important to acknowledge that infrastructures, such as basic facilities, facilitate effective learning for learners (Onen, 2024; Brown, 2024).

The challenge of infrastructural development in the Nigerian public tertiary system became obvious as funding of public institutions, irrespective of ownership, dwindled from the mid-1980s and was becoming more alarming by the early 1990s, the reason the Academic Staff Union of Universities embarked on a long-drawn

strike that birthed the Tertiary Education Trust Fund (TETFund) formally in 1993. The Tertiary Education Trust Fund (TETFund) is a metamorphosis from the Education Tax Fund (ETF) and later the Education Trust Fund (ETF), which was the outcome of the cry of the Academic Staff Union of Universities (ASUU). It was born because of the long-drawn ASUU strike and subject negotiations of 1992. It formally came into being through Act 7 of January 1993, tagged Education Tax Fund Act No. 7 of 1993 (TETFund's website home page, n.d.). The act establishing it was amended by Act 40 of 1998 and later repealed and replaced with the Tertiary Education Trust Fund Act of 2011. One of the basic functions of the Fund is infrastructural development intervention across public tertiary education institutions irrespective of whether they are owned by the national or sub-national government. Onuka et al. (2025) reported that most infrastructures in new universities across the country are almost entirely sponsored by TETFund. It appears state and federal governments merely establish new universities and hand over infrastructural (physical, instructional material, and equipment), research and publications, and among other things to stakeholders. Given this three-part mandate, it is important to examine how it can help create a strong base for significant improvements in infrastructure and human resources, especially in our colleges and universities through better facilities and teaching materials. This is crucial because having the right physical resources, skill people, and research is essential for providing quality higher education anywhere cannot be ignored. This is so because the availability of

physical and learning facilitation facilities, the right calibre of human resources, and research are pivotal to quality tertiary education provision in any clime. The need for TETFund, as it were, was due to the presence of heavy infrastructural decay across Nigerian national and sub-national higher education institution. Therefore, it appears that the establishment of TETFund aims to address these aspects of its mandate.

The abysmal state of infrastructures and the low level of staff development programmes in the Public Tertiary Education Institutions (PTEIs) were the result of the poor state of funding in the subsector for years. And this was captured by Oralu and Oladele (2015), when they found that the yearly budgetary allocations (2010 - 2020) to the subsector. The sub-sector was almost always less than 10% of the annual national budget, which was most often merely an allocation since the entire amount may not be released. Onuka (2005) observed that most of this money went into servicing recurring expenditure, while little or nothing was left for executing capital projects. The result is the decay hitherto experienced in terms of infrastructural provision in these institutions, both at the national and sub-national levels. This position was equally supported by Gambo and Fasanmi (2019), who found that there were a lot of challenges confronting the university education system in Nigeria, even at that time, because of inadequate funding of the public university system; the development resulted in incessant industrial disputes by virtually all members of the university community, including students, and of course there was also so much dilapidated infrastructure and so many learning facilities

that were not being renovated or replaced. Nevertheless, the issue of insufficient funds and its accessibility has persistently posed a significant challenge, despite the government's endeavours to create educational institutions such as colleges of education, polytechnics, and universities in Nigeria to equip students with the necessary skills and knowledge before their graduation. Undoubtedly, allocating sufficient funds to higher education institutions is the most effective approach to improving administration, planning, teaching quality, and programs, all of which are critical for institutional management (Ololube, 2016).

The case at the national level is like that of the states, if not much better. In its report on infrastructural projects nationwide from January 15 to February 2024, the Fund had several ongoing infrastructural projects in Kwara State: provision of fabrication equipment for Federal Polytechnic in Offa; various infrastructural facilities in Kwara State Polytechnic, fulfils Nigerian Army School of Education, Sobi-Ilorin (TETFund reconciled physical infrastructure projects in public tertiary institutions nationwide, 2024). This TETFund does in fulfilment of its mandate of project. The Fund fulfils this mandate by identifying the infrastructural needs of each institution in collaboration with them, estimating costs, and awarding contracts for the construction of infrastructure or the purchase of necessary equipment for these institutions (tetfund.org.ng, n. d.). Collaboration with each institution, costing them, and awarding the contracts for construction of the infrastructures or purchase of the needed equipment for the institutions

(tETFund.org.ng, n. d.). It was noted that as of 01 July 2024, the TETFund had reportedly funded some 5525 physical infrastructures nationwide. The availability of sufficient infrastructure and equipment, along with their effective use, would significantly enhance the delivery of instruction and learning, thereby improving the quality of tertiary education. The demand for laboratories and digital equipment is growing, and without the availability of suitable facilities and materials, teaching and learning, regardless of the mode, cannot be effectively conducted. This necessity led to the imperative of studying the work of TETFund in Kwara State, where limited literature existed regarding how successfully TETFund had fulfilled its mandate concerning infrastructural and staff development, as well as funding research beyond its own various reports. In Kwara State, there are 3 state government-owned Colleges of Education, including one technical, and the Nigerian Army School of Education, owned by the federal government, and 2 publicly owned universities (1 state, 1 federal) as of 2022, when this study began. There are also at least. As of 2022, this study identified a total of 8 public higher education institutions categorised as PTEIs, excluding monotechnics. The federal government owned three of these institutions, while the state government owned the remaining five out of these belonged to the federal government, while the remaining five were owned by the state government. The situation with the institutions, irrespective of ownership, is very similar to what obtains at the national level, if not worse, as revealed by the preliminary

study of the known Public Tertiary Education Institutions (PTEIs) in the state. Underfunding of public tertiary education institutions seems to be phenomenal in most of Sub-Saharan Africa. For instance, attesting to this phenomenon, Bakkabulindi (2005) observed that educational institutions in Uganda were being grossly underfunded. Kasozi (2009) concurred with him when he submitted that insufficient funding of public education has become a barrier to meeting publication. Kasozi and his colleagues believed that insufficient funding was the reason for the poor state of educational infrastructure and stunted development in Uganda. In Ghana, Newman and Duwiejua (2015) posited that the main sources of funds for education funds for education in Ghana are grants from the government, internally generated revenue, development partners, and fees from students. Thus, the government's block allocations to tertiary institutions are anything but adequate to meet all institutional financial obligations, including infrastructural and staff development, as well as formulated a policy based on the model, which led to the creation of the "Universities Funding Body." (2015), is not much different from elsewhere in Sub-Saharan Africa. This development let the Kenyan devise a funding model that has had constitutional backing since 2012. Kiamba also stated that the government also formulated a policy based on the model that birthed the "Universities Funding Body."

In Nigeria, the funding situation in provincially owned public tertiary education institutions is more acute than what obtains in federally owned institutions. According to Onuka et al. (2025),

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some state-owned tertiary exclusively on TETFund for funding infrastructure and covering tuition fees as part of their recurrent expenditure. Kwara, being part of Nigeria, has not been known to have a model for funding infrastructure Kwara, like many states in the Nigerian federation, does not have special funding arrangements for its tertiary education institutions, so it is with Kwara. In fact, Nwabuaku (2023) lamented the state of funding at Delta State University, Abraka, and its toll on infrastructural development and other budgetary heads in the institution. Therefore, all of them suffer a similar fate to that of the national tertiary education institutions, save for the intervention of TETFund.

The theoretical premise for funding education, according to Nwana (2000), is to provide quality in education provision. Onuka (2021) submitted that funding is the key to quality provision in education and other spheres. These submissions form the premise for the study. Quality education is the product of adequate funding and prudent spending. This is true because all that constitutes quality in education is a function of adequate funding. Furthermore, it is also obvious that the other elements of quality in education, such as inputs and processes, depend on the availability of adequate funds. For example, we expect adequate funding to enhance the quality of facilities/equipment, teachers, learners, laboratories, etc., assuming all other factors remain equal. Tamuno (1995) defines quality as libraries, etc., other things being equal. To Tamuno (1995), quality is the acceptability of the total environment of the educational system. In fact, Onuka (2021) postulated the fact that

everything that has to do with quality is a function of adequacy and prudent utilisation of available funds. The most effective way to achieve sustainable global development is through quality education. Thus, everyone has a role to play in improving the quality of education to meet the aspiration of the Nigerian Agenda 2030. Governments, teachers, schools, parents/students, host communities, industries, etc. have prominent roles to play. Quality cocurricular are reviewed at regular intervals to keep pace with global labour system to ensure that the curricula are reviewed at regular intervals to keep pace with global labour market demands, where learning and Infrastructures in educational institutions enhance the provision of quality education by facilitating learning in multiple ways. Institutions enhance the provision of quality education, as they aid learning facilitation in more ways than one. These include the library and its stock serving as a warehouse for harvesting knowledge; other teaching and learning aids; and the technologies for facilitating learning, especially in this post-COVID era of technology-enhanced learning coming on the front burner. This equally informed the need to undertake a study on TETFund's role in facility provision in public tertiary institutions across the country.

Thus, it is imperative for a study to unearth the extent to which public tertiary education institutions in Kwara State had benefitted from TETFund's institutional infrastructural and staff development project. Therefore, it was deemed imperative to study and ascertain the level of TETFund's intervention in infrastructural and staff developments and research funding in

public tertiary education institutions in Kwara State, Nigeria. This study was created to investigate how TETFund supports infrastructure, staff development, and research funding in public tertiary education institutions in Kwara State. The study also ascertained the level of budgetary allocations to capital project development in these institutions by their owners, especially between 2012 and 2022.

Research Questions

The following research questions were answered in this study:

1. What are the perceived sources of institutional funding in public tertiary institutions in Kwara State from 2012 to 2022?
2. What is the current state of available infrastructure in public tertiary institutions in Kwara State?
3. What is the level of TETFund's infrastructural intervention in public tertiary institutions in Kwara State between 2012 and 2022?

METHODS

The study employed mixed methods design (quantitative and qualitative) to examine TETFund's interventions in infrastructural and staff development, as well as research funding, within state and federal institutions in Kwara State. The population for the study was made up of the 8 public tertiary institutions, consisting of four colleges of education, including the Nigerian Army School of Education, since it is owned by the federal government and it equally benefits from TETFund infrastructural development, two public universities type, and one of each these were classified by types, and one of each type was selected using simple random sampling. In the

final selection, two state institutions and one federal institution made up the sample. They were one university, one college of education, and one polytechnic, respectively.

Data was collected using the Budgetary Financing Distribution Proforma with 15 HoDs, 3 DAPs, and 3 librarians from their respective departments/units, where most of the infrastructure and equipment were domiciled. A TETFund-sponsored infrastructural observation checklist was used to record the quantum of TETFund-sponsored infrastructures vis-à-vis the other infrastructure independent members of the institution communities, though guided by our contact persons in the respective institutions who were independently and discreetly selected to assist the researchers. They were not research assistants but guides. The checklist was content validated by 10 experts, and the computed content validity ratio was 0.87. The data collection lasted one and a half weeks as the researchers distributed themselves among these institutions for the exercise. Fifteen selected core officers (one bursar each, one DAP each, and one librarian from each institution. Data was analysed using percentages and qualitative analytical methods, and pictorials were used as an addition to quantitative data collection. The data arising from the exercise were analysed using percentages and qualitative analytical methods and pictorials to explain the quantitative results.

The population was stratified by interest groups, and an appropriate number was proportionately chosen from each group. The sample is as shown in Table 1.

Table 1: The Composition of the Sample for the Study

Interest group	number per institution	Total
Council/Management	03	09
Students	10	30
Non-Academic Staff	05	15
Academic staff	10	30
HoDs	05	15
DAPs	01	03
Deans	03	09
Director of Works	01	03
Total	46	114

Results and Discussion

Research Question 1: What are the perceived sources of institutional funding in public tertiary institutions in Kwara State from 2012 to 2022?

The quantitative findings from this study are presented in Tables 1, 2 and 3.

Table 2: Perceived Current Sources of Funds Available to the institutions (Current Budgetary Funding)

Part A: Sources of Fund other than Tetfund			
S/N	Sources of Fund	Yes (%)	No (%)
1	Bursary awards to students	65	35
2	Students' scholarship/bursary	52	48
3	Loan to students	21	79
4	Relevant Ministry	16	84
5	Donation: a. Buildings	24	76
6	Donation: b. Equipment	16	84
7	Donation: c. Machinery	20	80
8	Donation: d. Utility Vehicles	25	75
9	Sponsorship	33	67
10	Tuition fee	64	36
11	Levies paid by students	45	55
12	Publications	27	73
13	Events/Rentals	32	68
14	Special Endowments	14	86
15	Research/Innovations/Inventions	12	88
16	Donations	44	56
17	Sponsorship/scholarship to staff	32	68
18	Capital project	39	61

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19	Research grants	32	68
20	Fellowships	16	84
21	Rentals	28	72
22	Alumni contributions	27	73
23	Lease financing/Borrowing	00	100

Part B: TETFund's Involvement in Funding Capital Projects

1	Physical structures	100	-
2	Equipment	100	-
3	Furniture	100	-
4	Research	100	-
5	Training/staff development	100	-

Table 2 presents the perception of stakeholders on whether each of the indicated sources contributes to funding of public higher education institutions in Kwara State. Column 2 indicates the perceived source; row 3 shows the percentage that perceived it as a source, row column 4 depicts the percentage of those A close look at part B of the analysis in Table 2 shows that all stakeholders confirmed that TETFund was completely involved in building institutional resources and developing people development. In other words, all respondents agreed TETFund was fully involved in providing infrastructure research a 2012–2022.

The respondents confirmed that TETFund indeed limited its activities to the mandate outlined in the Act that established it, as amended from the respondents' perspective, the owners of the institutions are not providing sufficient support for institutional infrastructure and human development, both of which are crucial for facilitating high-quality education that leads to a strong employability rate for graduates. a high employability rate for their output/product. Besides, they are involved in

lease financing, which could have boosted capital development within the campuses. Other sources of funding exploited by the institutions from the responses are marginally yielding the required dividends in terms of the total amount of funds expected from each of the listed sources. This is perhaps what has been responsible for the lack of adequate funding of these institutions, thus propelling incessant academic program disruptions in Nigerian public tertiary institutions (Onuka et al., 2025; NASU's struggle and ASUU strike). Therefore, ASUU deserves some credit for its ingenuity in establishing the TETFund.7). Therefore, some credit must be given to ASUU for ingenuity in the establishment of TETFund. The result also confirms the poor state of funding of government institutions in Nigeria (Olatunji and Onuka, 2024). The summary result from the analysis of the interviews also supports the fact that in Nigeria, governments keep establishing new tertiary institutions without commensurate funding by them but depend on TETFund for infrastructural and equipment provision for the newly

established institutions, which development does not seem to be coming to an end soon.

state of available infrastructure in public tertiary institutions in Kwara State?

Research Question 2: What is the current

Table 3: Level of Facility Availability, Usability, and Adequacy with Percentage Contribution by TETFund in the three Institutions

S/N	Facilities	Available	Not Available	Adequate	Not Adequate	Usable	Not Usable	TETFund sponsored
1.	Laboratories	100%		33%	67%	100%	-	65%
2.	Library	75%	17%	83%	17%	100%	-	40%
3.	e Library	83%	17%	33%	67%	100%	-	50%
4.	Sport	100%		67%	33%	100%	-	50%
5.	Teaching	100%		50%	50%	100%	-	75%
6.	Internet	50%	50%	33%	67%	67%	33%	25%
7.	Classroom	100%		50%	50%	100%	-	64%
8.	Seminar Rooms	100%		50%	50%	100%	-	42%
9.	Common Rooms	83%	17%	33%	67%	83%	17%	20%
10.	Health/medical	100%		50%	50%	100%	-	31%
11.	Lecture Theatres	100%		33%	67%	100%	-	56%
12.	Auditoria	83%	17%	67%	33%	83%	17%	50%
13.	Reagents	67%	33%	33%	67%	67%	33%	indeterminate
14.	Staff Offices	100%		67%	33%	100%		50%
15.	Administrative Buildings	100%		67%	33%	100%		50%
16.	Technical equipment	100%		67%	33%	83%	17%	
17.	Class/Lecture Room	83%	17%	33%	67%	67%	33%	41%
18.	Conveniences	83%	17%	33%	67%	67%	33%	-
19.	Water supply system	100%		67%	33%	100%		30%

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20.	Power supply equipment	100%	33%	67%	100%	36%
21.	Other sanitary facilities, e.g., sewage	100%	50%	50%	100%	-

Table Aggregate of facilities provided by TETFund in the three institutions computed from data harvested through the observation checklist used by the researchers. TETFund primarily provided the majority of the usable equipment and facilities, as indicated in the column. In the newer institutions, whether owned by the state or federal, they were provided by TETFund, while many of the renovated infrastructures are also provided by TETFund.

Table 3 shows the quantum of available infrastructures in the institutions after aggregation vis-à-vis what is expected in proportion to the population of users or uses, their adequacies and then usability (utility). Column 9 of the Table depicts the proportion of contribution by TETFund towards these infrastructures. On average, it can be inferred that TETFund contributed over 50% of functioning facilities in these institutions. But these will dwindle soon, because of the continued establishment of multiplicity of higher education institutions without commensurate funding from government sources especially with respect

to infrastructural and human development as well as research except the expectation that TETFund will fund these important aspects of institutional development for functionality (Onuka, et al, 2025; Onen, 2024). This development suggests that retaining TETFund and improving on its funding is imperative for continuing existence and functioning of these institutions for greater Nigeria, since functional tertiary education provision is very pivotal to sustainable national development. To stop the phenomena of poor budgetary allocation to public tertiary institutions, if the desired quality output were to be realised, public tertiary education institutions must resort to public-private partnership.

Figure 1 is a supporting picture of some of the infrastructural undertakings of TETFund in these institutions to show that the Fund is involved in providing virtually all forms of infrastructure and facilities. Figure 2 depicts the TETFund is responsible for facilitating these facilities by TETFund.

Ion.

Figure 1 and Figure 2: The picture of some equipment and Library stocked with books provided by TETFund in an Institution

Research Question 3: What is the level of TETFund’s infrastructural intervention in public tertiary institutions in Kwara State between 2012 and 2022?

Table 4: The Level of TETFund’s Capital Development Project Interventions in Public Tertiary Education Institutions in Kwara State (2012-2022)

Type of TETFund Intervention	Percentage of Provision by Fund’s Intervention	by Other Sources
a. Physical structures	80	20
b. Equipment	70	30
c. Furniture	84	16
d. Research*	100	-
e. Training/staff development*	92	08

*Their inclusion stems from the fact that in this study, they are seen as human capital development.

This is an aggregation from the data harvested through the facility observation sheet and responses from relevant stakeholders about Research and staff development. A critical perusal and inferences from the Table shows that the perception of stakeholders was that in the

area of capital and human developments, TETFund was involved in providing infrastructure from 2012 to 2022 as shown by the analysis of the data from the physical observation of the available and functional infrastructures such as buildings, equipment, which includes library equipment, learning materials, furniture, research and training cum staff development up to the tune of 85% on the

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average. In the supporting interview, most of the interviewees ascertain that they have benefited from staff development programmes sponsored by TETFund, research projects (institutional-based research and national research funding. In one of the institutions, it was reported that officials from the Ministry took away some of the furniture provided by TETFund. The TETFund has significantly contributed to the development of physical infrastructure in Nigerian universities, including the construction of new buildings and the provision of instructional materials, which have positively impacted academic staff performance (Fashiku et al., 2023). Despite these efforts, infrastructural decay remains an issue, as TETFund often focuses on new constructions rather than rehabilitating existing structures (Fashiku et al., 2024).

The physical buildings and other learning facilities were provided in these institutions by TETFund. The state government seldom provides such facilities, and so they rely heavily on the Fund for the provision of these important learning enabling environments in the institution. This confirmation of the observation

made by Onuka et al (2025) that most state governments have abandoned the provision of infrastructural facilities in their own state owned tertiary institutions to TETFund. This finding also supports the findings of Gambo and Fasanmi (2019) and Nwabuaku (2023) respectively on the poor state of physical facilities in Nigerian public universities and Delta State University, Abraka. Those interviewed confirmed this as well, that save for TETFund, the state of infrastructures in public tertiary institutions in the state were being 'malnourished'. Respondents generally agreed that the inadequacy of available funds prevented proper maintenance of the limited infrastructures. Also, those interviewed attest to the fact that most of new physical facilities and equipment as well as human development and research funding in these institutions had come from TETFund intervention projects and programme.

Figure 3 depicts a library refurbished and stocked with books sponsored by the Fund. Figures 4-6 provide evidence of additional infrastructure contributions made by the TETFund to these institutions.

Figure 3: Another TETFund furnished library in another institution

Figures 4-6: Show some other infrastructural contributions by TETFund in Nigeria institutions

All these pictures are just samples of what TETFund did in these institutions. This is an attestation to the claim by the Fund to have provided 5525 infrastructures and facilities nationwide in the last few years nationwide. In

2024, TETFund reportedly provided over 16 million Naira worth of fabrication equipment for Federal Polytechnic, Offa; various facilities and equipment worth 127 million Naira at Kwara State Polytechnic, Ilorin and 130 million Naira worth variety of facilities and equipment at the Nigerian Army School of Education, Sobi-Ilorin (TETFund.org.ng, 2024). The field visits

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confirmed the findings of this study. The claims were also supported by this pictorial evidence.

Conclusion

The research critically investigated the impact of the Tertiary Education Trust Fund (TETFund) in improving infrastructure and personnel development in public tertiary institutions in Kwara State, Nigeria. The findings demonstrated that TETFund initiatives significantly enhanced the physical infrastructure of numerous institutions, including the construction and repair of lecture halls, laboratories, libraries, and information and communication technology facilities. These modifications have helped to create a more conducive learning and teaching environment, which has a direct influence on academic delivery and institutional effectiveness.

In addition to infrastructure, the study found that TETFund has played an important role in staff development by providing funds for academic training, conference attendance, and research awards. Beneficiaries reported higher academic credentials, exposure to the best global practices, and increased research outputs. However, various problems, such as delays in cash disbursement, insufficient awareness of available grants, and bureaucratic bottlenecks, were identified as impediments to the most effective use of TETFund initiatives. Finally, the data from Kwara State shows that the TETFund remains an important tool for revitalising public tertiary education in Nigeria. While the benefits are clear, more monitoring, openness, and institutional capability are required to access and administer the monies successfully. Strengthening these areas would guarantee that

TETFund efforts continue to support long-term improvement in Nigeria's higher education system.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following suggestions were put forward for consideration by policymakers and other relevant stakeholders:

1. Based on the performance of the Fund so far, it should further stress to continue to fulfil this tripartite mandate of infrastructural provision, staff development and research funding, which has done excellently well so far.
2. Federal and state governments should devise some other way of sourcing funds for their tertiary education institutions to augment the efforts of TETFund in terms of these essential tripartite inputs needed in the institutions for functioning as well as bringing out quality and employable graduates.
3. TETFund's focus should be expanded to include the rehabilitation of existing infrastructure and ensuring equitable access to staff development programs could further improve educational outcomes.
4. Government should also evolve a practicable all stakeholders' financing solution to address the infrastructural and staff development deficit to complement the efforts of TETFund and thereby raise the bar of quality in each state and Nigeria as a whole.
5. The governments could also consider public-private partnerships to upscale the facilities and improve the staff in their tertiary institutions.

Acknowledgements

The investigators express gratitude to TETFUND (Nigeria) for providing the funds for this research. The researchers are also grateful to all

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institutions in which the research was conducted and regulatory bodies like the NUC and NCCE, and indeed all our research assistants.

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Irish Journal of Educational Practice

Irish J. Edu Pract
Volume: 8; Issue: 04
July-August, 2025
ISSN: 2383 – 6345
Impact Factor: 5.46

Advance Scholars Publication
Published by International Institute of Advance
Scholars Development
<https://aspjournals.org/Journals/index.php/ijep>

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